

Reference list and tool/learning source registry for excavation data modeling

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1. Excavation data modeling reference list

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2. Excavation data modeling PPTs

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3. Data modeling tools and learning facilities registry

A. Tools useful in data modelling

- GraphDB - <https://graphdb.ontotext.com/>

GraphDB is an enterprise ready Semantic Graph Database, compliant with W3C Standards. Semantic graph databases or RDF triplestores, provide the core infrastructure for data modelling. Graph DB can be accessed via the ARIADNEplus VRE providing access to the ARIADNEplus Knowledge Base, including all the partner data as a Linked Open Data set and modelled according to the ARIADNE ontology. Using GraphDB, researchers can explore the knowledge base with the available web GUI or programmatically with SPARQL queries. Documentation (KB-guide-v1.0) is provided as a python notebook, a PDF file or in Markdown format at <https://data.d4science.net/EvVX>. The python notebook can be run on the JupyterHub tool also available in the ARIADNEplus Lab VRE at https://ariadne.d4science.org/group/ariadneplus_lab/jupyterhub. The guide also contains several examples of queries that can be run on the ARIADNE Knowledge base. Users should copy the notebook to a Jupyter instance in order to play with it and to create their own notebooks for their analysis of the ARIADNEplus Knowledge Base.

- OntoRefine - <https://disc-semantic.uibk.ac.at/ontorefine>

OntoRefine is a data transformation tool, based on OpenRefine, that is integrated into GraphDB by OntoText. The environment adds support for direct RDF conversion through a SPARQL endpoint.

- Sparnatural - <https://sparnatural.eu/>

A Javascript based system allowing the user to query an RDF graph with a graphic interface and without any SPARQL to write.

- Protégé-Ontop - <https://protege.stanford.edu/> & <https://ontop-vkg.org/>

Protégé is an open source ontology editor and knowledge management system. Ontop-Protégé is a plugin for designing and testing a Virtual Knowledge Graph (VKG) specification. (See also <https://halshs.archives-ouvertes.fr/halshs-03561376v2/file/MappingOntop.pdf>).

- Karma - <https://usc-isi-i2.github.io/karma/>

Karma is an information integration tool that enables users to quickly and easily integrate data from a variety of data sources including databases, spreadsheets, delimited text files, XML, JSON, KML and Web APIs. Users integrate information by modeling it according to an ontology of their choice using a graphical user interface that automates much of the process. Karma learns to recognize the mapping of data to ontology classes and then uses the ontology to propose a model that ties together these classes.

- SHACL - <https://shacl-play.sparna.fr/play/>

A tool for verifying the conformity of the knowledge graphs with the generic models used.

- X3ML Toolkit (FORTH)

Consists of a set of software components that assist the data provisioning process for information integration. The key components of the toolkit are:

a) X3ML Mapping Definition Language

(<https://github.com/isl/x3ml/blob/master/docs/x3ml-language.md>) is an XML based language that describes schema mappings,

b) 3M Mapping Memory Manager (<https://demos.isl.ics.forth.gr/3m>) is a web application suite containing several software sub-components and exploits several external services.

c) X3ML Engine (<https://github.com/isl/x3ml>) realises the transformation of the source records to the target format

d) RDF Visualiser (<https://demos.isl.ics.forth.gr/RDFV-Demo/>) is a generic browsing mechanism that gives the user a flexible, highly configurable, detailed overview of a dataset/database encoded in RDF.

- CRITERIA - <https://github.com/chin-rcip/CRITERIA> & Mermaid - <https://mermaid-js.github.io/mermaid/#/>

A tool for the automatic transform of RDF data into visualised graphs

- diagrams.net Libraries - https://github.com/chin-rcip/diagrams.net_libraries

A library created by the Canadian Heritage Information Network (CHIN) to facilitate the visualisation of data models based on CIDOC CRM and its extensions when using the diagrams.net tool (<https://app.diagrams.net/>).

- AIRtable - <https://www.airtable.com/>

A spreadsheet-database hybrid cloud collaboration service, with the features of a database applied onto a spreadsheet.

- Vocabulary Matching Tool (VMT) - <https://heritagedata.org/vocabularyMatchingTool/>

The Vocabulary Matching Tool developed as part of the ARIADNE H2020 project builds on a tool originally developed during the ARIADNE FP7 Project by the University of Wales. It can be used for the creation of mappings from locally used terms/concepts to the Getty Art & Architecture Thesaurus (AAT). The aim is to identify subject mappings from source terms/concepts to AAT concepts that are likely to be useful to assist subsequent data searching and browsing. The creation of mappings to a common spine vocabulary enables improved opportunities for multilingual subject access and cross search, by aggregating mappings from multiple data partners. The set of mappings created may be exported to JSON or delimited text (CSV) format for use in other applications. The tool is accessible also via the ARIADNEplus VRE.

- PeriodO - <https://perio.do/>

The PeriodO gazetteer service allows the definition of temporal intervals as web resources, using a label and two absolute dates giving the earliest start and the latest stop of each interval. The service also allows clustering period resources in collections, thus facilitating their exploration.

- DARIAH Back Bone Thesaurus - <https://www.backbonethesaurus.eu/>

A model for sustainable interoperable thesauri maintenance, developed in the European Union Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH). Its development aims at designing and establishing an overarching thesaurus for the humanities (BackBone Thesaurus, BBT for short). Relevant work focuses on identifying the top-level-concepts (facets and hierarchies) that will become a common basis for thesaurus building in an effort to meet the demands for objectivity and interdisciplinarity.

B. Learning facilities

- CIDOC CRM Game Digital - <https://www.cidoc-crm-game.org/node/39> (downloadable version), <https://ontomatchgame.huma-num.fr/> (online version)

CIDOC CRM the Game is an open source initiative that aims to promote wider adoption of the CIDOC CRM standard through facilitating the learning process for beginning users/learners. The Game provides a fun way to visualise and play with the ontology in relation to real world documentation scenarios.

- CIDOC CRM tutorials. <https://cidoc-crm.org/tutorialPageRes>

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